

**Faculty of Technical Sciences,
University of Novi Sad**

**Hybrid event
December 6th 2022
Novi Sad, Serbia**

Organizers:

Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Institute of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of
Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia

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PREFACE

On behalf of the Scientific and Organizing Committees, it is my pleasure to present the Abstract book of the 2nd DIFENEW Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia and Institute of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia as the part of the activities within International Student Conference DISC2022, which was held in hybrid mode on 6th December 2022. DISC2022 was organized by the Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health, Faculty of the Serbian-Slovak Bilateral Project “*Microplastics impact on occurrence of plasticizers in surface water and effects on human health - PLASTICINE*“. The Project is supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of Serbia and Slovak Research and Development Agency.

DISC2022 conference was a multidisciplinary forum where the research results in the field of Environmental Engineering, Environmental Monitoring, Environmental and Health Risk Assessment, Occupational Health and Safety, Sustainable Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety Project Management and Civil Engineering were shared between students and their professors from the entire world. At the same time, the event was the place for the promotion of the PLASTICINE results to a wider audience.

Since the main objective of DISC2022 is to encourage young researchers to exchange ideas and experiences, to present the results, raise the knowledge, and to expand scientific and professional networks, it is my great pleasure to inform you that, once again, a record number of abstracts was submitted. Moreover, this year, for the first time we had the special session dedicated for the presentation of ongoing projects and future events.

I would like to express my sincere thanks to all members of Scientific and Organizing committees, session chairs, presenters, projects coordinators as well as to many others who contributed to the success of DISC2022.

We are confident that the solid foundation created by the DIFENEW and PLASTICINE projects will continue to build up and strengthen the unique international network of young students, colleagues and experts.

Editor

In Novi Sad, December 2022

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IN SILICO INSIGHT INTO THE ENDOCRINE DISRUPTING POTENTIAL OF BISPHENOL A ANALOGUES ON ANDROGEN RECEPTOR

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Abstract: In recent years, bisphenol A (BPA) is being replaced by its analogues in the production of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins, due to the recognized negative biological effects of BPA. However, the endocrine-disrupting properties of these BPA substitutes have not been tested sufficiently. The aim of this study was to evaluate *in silico* if BPA structural analogues act as androgen receptor agonist considering the molecular properties of the analyzed compounds. The binding affinity of BPA and its 25 analogues for the androgen receptor (AR; PDB entry code: 5CJ6) was predicted using GOLD molecular docking tool and expressed as ChemPLP fitness score. Molecular properties were calculated using an online SwissADME tool. ChemPLP fitness score for the pre-existing co-crystallized ligand was 68.62, for BPA was 67.34, while the scores for the analyzed analogues were in the range of 9.40-70.48. Three compounds did not show binding activity (4,4'-bis(N-carbamoyl-4-methylbenzene sulfonamide) diphenylmethane, Bisphenol A bis(diphenyl phosphate), and urea urethane), three compounds showed higher score than BPA (bisphenol B, Bis(3-allyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) sulfone, and 1,7-bis(4-hydroxyphenylthio)-3,5-dioxahseptane), while the rest of the compounds showed a binding affinity similar to BPA. The highest binding affinity was observed for bisphenol B (70.48). The 23 out of 26 compounds had molecular weight, MW < 500 g/mol, 24 out of 26 compounds had polar surface area, PSA < 140Å², and 20 out of 26 had the average logP < 4.15 (an indicator of lipophilicity), which indicated good oral bioavailability. The obtained results suggest that BPA and its analogues could interfere with the androgen receptor which indicate the endocrine-disrupting potential of these compounds. Further studies are needed in order to determine the biological effects of BPA substitutes.

Keywords: *Bisphenol A; Endocrine Disruptors; Docking; In silico; Androgen Receptors.*

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